

FACTORS CAUSING DEMONSTRATIVENESS AND AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENCE

Gozal Sultanovna Yunusova

Doctor of philosophy (PhD) in psychological sciences,
associate professor.

Fergana State University.

Meliqoziyeva Mardona

2nd year student of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10060181>

Abstract. This article is written about the factors that cause demonstrativeness and aggressiveness in teenage boys and girls, and the scientific views of psychologists who conducted scientific research on this topic were analyzed in the article.

Key words: aggression, demonstrativeness, boys, girls, psychologists, upbringing, teenager.

Аннотация. В данной статье написано о факторах, вызывающих демонстративность и агрессивность у мальчиков и девочек-подростков, а также проанализированы научные взгляды психологов, проводивших научные исследования на эту тему.

Ключевые слова: агрессия, демонстративность, мальчики, девочки, психологи, воспитание, подросток.

Today, in a situation where the upbringing of a well-rounded human personality is more urgent than ever before, the spiritual and social vitality of the young generation is of great importance in the moral and spiritual development of the young generation.

In such a tense and dangerous situation, we, parents, teachers, the public, and the community should increase vigilance and awareness in this matter. We should raise our children ourselves, not leave them in someone else's hands. Buning uchun yoshlarimiz bilan ko'proq gaplashish, ularning qalbiga quloq solish, dardini bilish, muammolarini yechish uchun amaliy ko'mak berishimiz kerak. Bu borada uyushmagan yoshlar bilan ishlashga alohida e'tibor qaratishimiz zarur. Bu vazifalarni bajarishda biz asirlar mobaynida shakillangan milliy an'analarimizga, ajdodlarimizning boy merosiga tayanamiz. Farzandlarimiz zamonaviy bilim va kasb hunarlarni, xorijiy tillarni egallashlari, har tomonlama sog'lom va barkamol bo'lib, hayotdan munosib o'rin topishlari uchun barcha kuch va imkoniyatlarimizni safarbar etamiz." Yuqoridagi mamlakatimiz rahbarining jonkuyar fikrlaridan kelib chiqqan holda yurtimiz kelajagi bo'lgan yoshlar, xususan o'smirlarning psixologik holati, ularning

xulqidagi namoyishkorlik va tajovuzkorlik darajasini kamaytirish nuqtayi nazaridan mavzu dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Five important initiatives were put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in March 2019. This includes the tasks of widely involving young people in culture, art and sports, forming in them the ability to use modern information technologies correctly, improving the culture of reading, and ensuring the employment of women. representatives of agencies and organizations, including the Youth Affairs Agency, the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Physical Education and Sports, the Ministry of Development of Information Technologies and Communications, the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the Agency for Information and Mass Communications, the Republic of Spirituality and The work done by the employees of the Enlightenment Center and Writers' Union and the work to be done in the next years were reviewed.

The knowledge that we give to the young generation is considered a foundation for the future of our country. The stronger we make the foundation, the more durable it will be, it will not fall in any situation, it will acquire a look that will amaze with its awesomeness over the years. Today, the reforms, decrees and orders carried out by our President are efforts to strengthen this foundation as much as possible. Today, only young people who have an independent and firm approach to the dangerous processes taking place in the global arena, who are mentally and physically fit, can resist.

When defining the identity of a teenager, it is necessary to take into account his attitude to the environment, social events, and people. From the research conducted by psychologists, it can be seen that the majority of teenagers correctly understand spiritual and moral concepts such as determination, modesty, pride, sincerity, kindness. In their life experience, as a result of mastering the basics of science, a stable religious and scientific outlook is formed, on the basis of which moral ideals begin to emerge.

It is known that during adolescence, a teenager's "I" is formed again. The people around him, especially his attitude towards himself, his interests, and the direction of his values will change dramatically.

At the age of adolescence, the most important psychological trait - the emergence of a sense of adulthood or adulthood is of particular importance. The feeling of greatness is expressed in the socio-moral sphere, mental activity, interest, attitude, enjoyment process, external forms of behavior. By studying the psychological features characteristic of adolescence, it is possible to

understand the ways of the formation, development and maturation of the adolescent personality and the direct influence of biological and social factors that affect it. Puberty affects the behavior of a teenager at this age as the main biological tool. But this is a direct effect.

The inconsistency that appears in young adolescents in relation to older adolescents is not due to their sexual maturity, but the surrounding conditions, the attitude of parents and siblings in the family, neighborhood, that is, social conditions. It is necessary to connect with the secret. These social conditions have a direct impact on the behavior of adolescents by changing their psychological climate, bad behavior, stubbornness, failure to recognize their shortcomings. can prevent such negative traits. During this period, the teenager is in a state where he has said goodbye to a happy childhood, but has not yet found his place in adult life. A teenager tries to solve complex life problems without correctly assessing his abilities and strength, but because of his superficial thinking ability, he allows a number of shortcomings in his daily life. But he prefers to argue with adults than to admit his mistake. He does not like people who criticize him, every criticism seems to be a sign of contempt for him, a deliberate act. He tries to act independently and arbitrarily, he does not pay attention to the advice of adults.

Demonstration - purposeful, conscious behavior to make a certain impression on others, to appear in one's own way, acts of "playfulness" in behavior and excessive self-esteem and emphasizing the "I-image"¹. Adolescence is a transitional, complex, difficult, critical period. Often it is experienced with a heavy head, which leads to deviations. In some cases, the following cases are observed in the behavior of minors:

- consumption of alcohol, drugs,
- theatrical and suicidal behavior of teenagers, their
- joining groups and subcultures united under different ideas is visible.

Scientists have unanimously come to the conclusion that demonstrativeness is one of the characteristic features of adolescent behavior. According to A.E.Lichko, the demonstrative reaction is "the most common among the affective reactions in the behavior of adolescents."

The desire to stand out from others is carried out in several directions, depending on the situation, it switches from one style to another, or if the result of the style at the same time is satisfactory, the teenager may not change the style. The first method is to arouse respect and admiration and sympathy for

¹ Кравченко А.С. Мотивация демонстративного поведения: автореф. Дис. ... Канд. Психол. Наук. М.: МГУ им. М.В.Ломоносова, 2001. 102 с.

one's personality. This method works well at school and at home. In this case, the teenager tries to distinguish himself by his success in studies, sports or participation in some club. Often, a teenager explains his failures in education with external factors. In addition, actions aimed at gaining the compassion and sympathy of those around. Various tricks are chosen for this. From telling them stories about their bad luck, going into hysterics, fainting, and even getting sick.

The third method is to attract the attention of others in a negative way. In the behavior of a teenager, boldness, clowning, rudeness, deliberate violation of discipline, going against the opinion of the majority and other deviations in behavior. Demonstrative escape and demonstrative suicide are among them.

According to G. Parens, aggressiveness is self-defense and protection of one's right. A.A Rean and S.L Solovyova also put forward the same opinion. Aggression can cause the manifestation of unpleasant characteristics of a person's character. Bullying in the form of fearlessness, inability to defend one's rights in the form of fear. Also, aggression varies with other types of delinquent and criminal behavior. Changes in the forms of aggressiveness are characteristic for teenagers.

L.M. Semenyuk (1996) conducted a study on the topic of different forms of aggression at different stages of adolescence. According to him, 10-11 year olds show more physical aggression. In them, relative aggression is less noticeable than all types of aggression. Teenagers aged 12-13 show more negativity, then physical and verbal aggression. In 14-15-year-old teenagers, verbal aggressiveness reaches the first level. Physical and relational types of aggression, as well as the level of negativity, increase significantly. There are gender differences in the manifestation of aggressive reactions. The method of physical aggression is more noticeable in boys. In girls, verbal aggression, indirect methods of aggression, as well as the level of negativity increase.²

The relationship between brothers and sisters in the family serves as the basis for the adolescent to master the manifestation of his aggression. This opinion was reflected in Felson's research (Richardson D. Beron R. 1997). As a result of this study, it was found that adolescents direct the greater part of physical and verbal aggression to their siblings. It was found that the parents' attitude towards the aggressiveness of the child affects the relationship between the child and the parents. Parents, while trying to eliminate negative

² К.Ю Гуляева «Агрессивность в подростковом возрасте и ее коррекция» УДК 159.96+159.94+316.6 23.12.2006г.

relationships between children, can cause these negative relationships to expand again³.

This is clearly visible in the relative form of aggression and negativity. The manifestation of aggression in a teenager or how it manifests itself depends on the family environment in which he lives, the peer group, the macro environment (educational institution), the traditions of the society in which he lives. It depends on the customs and traditions and the type of information flowing to him. The family plays a crucial role in this. This includes the relationship of spouses to each other in the family, the relationship between parents and children, moral rules in the family, worldview and plans and goals of the family.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019 yil 8 oktyabr "O'zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish kontseptsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi PF-5847-sonli Farmoni.
2. Кравченко А.С. Мотивация демонстративного поведения: автореф. Дис. Канд. Психол. Наук. М.: МГУ им. М.В.Ломоносова, 2001. 102 с.
3. К.Ю.Гуляева «Агрессивность в подростковом возрасте и ее коррекция» УДК 159.96+159.94+316.6 23.12.2006 г.
4. Р.Берон Д.Ричардсон – Агрессия спб 1997. 104 ст.
5. Yunusova, G. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL INFLUENCE OF MASS CULTURE ON THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL VALUES OF ADOLESCENTS. В INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (Т. 3, Выпуск 10, сс. 447–453)
6. Yunusova, G. (2023). DISADAPTATION AND ITS MANIFESTATION IN ADOLESCENT BEHAVIOR. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(10), 47-52.
7. Yunusova, G. Z. (2023). FARZANDLARNING SIBLING MAQOMINI OILADAGI MUNOSABATLARGA TA'SIRI. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(17), 44-52.
8. Юнусова, Г. (2023). ЎСМИР ЁШЛИ БОЛАЛАРНИ ОИЛАВИЙ ҲАЁТГА МАЪНАВИЙ ЖИҲАТДАН ТАЙЁРЛАШДА ОНА ШАХСИНИНГ ТАЪСИРИ. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(5 Part 3), 69-75.
9. Sultanovna, Y.G. (2023). Social-Psychological Factors Forming Deviant Behavior In Teenagers And Their Prevention. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 20, 151-155.

³ Р.Берон Д.Ричардсон – Агрессия спб 1997. 104 ст.

10. Sul'tonovna, Y. G. Z. (2023). O 'SMIRLARDA ASSOTSIAL XULQNI SHAKLLANTIRUVCHI IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK OMILLAR. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(5), 1357-1367.
11. Sul'tonovna, Y.G. Z., & Axatjon o'g'li, I.A. (2023). O 'ZBEK OILALARIDANIZO VA AJRRIMLARNINGYUZAGA KELISHINING PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARI. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(5), 1348-1356.
12. YG Sul'tonovna. (2023). O'QUVCHILARDA INTERNETGA QARAMLIK SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARI. FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES 2 (21), 18-25
13. Юнусова Г. //Результаты изучения представлений о будущем у подростков, воспитывающихся в неполных узбекских семьях// Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2011. – №. 3. – С. 389-394.
14. Юнусова Г.С. //Развитие воображения молодежи и подростков, воспитывающихся в благополучных и неблагополучных семьях// Theoretical & Applied science. №. 6. 2013. 91-94.
15. Yunusova G.S. //To'liq va noto'liq oilalardagi ona shaxsining farzand ijtimoiy tasavvurlariga ta'siri// Psixol.f.d. ilmiy daraj. olish uchun yozilgan diss. avtoref.- T., O'zMU 2019.
16. Юнусова Гузаль Султановна, Исроилов Абдоржон Ахатжон угли //ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СЕМЕЙНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ В ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯХ УЗБЕКСКИХ УЧЕНЫХ// Образование и инновационные исследования 2022 год. № 5. 284-287 стр.
17. G.S.Yunusova //THE OUTCOMES OF A STUDY PREPARING BOYS AND GIRLS AT YOUNG AGE FOR FAMILY LIFE IN CONDITION OF UZBEKISTAN// The Way of Science. 2021. № 6 (88). 84-87 pages.
18. Yunusova G. S. //THE OUTCOMES OF A STUDY PREPARING BOYS AND GIRLS AT YOUNG AGE FOR FAMILY LIFE IN CONDITION OF UZBEKISTAN// The Way of Science. 2014. С. 84.
19. Юнусова Гузал Султоновна, Турдиматова Елноза Эркинжоновна //РОЛЬ СЕМЬИ В ПРОЯВЛЕНИИ АГРЕССИВНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ У ПОДРОСТКОВ// Образование и инновационные исследования. 2022 год № 11. 378-381 стр.
20. Юнусова Гузаль Султановна. //Развитие воображения молодежи и подростков, воспитывающихся в благополучных и неблагополучных семьях// Theoretical & Applied Science. № 6 (2).2013. 91-94 pages.

21. Юнусова Гузаль //Особенности взаимоотношений родителей с детьми-подростками в полных и неполных семьях// Молодой ученый. 2015. № 13 (93). С. 757-760.
22. Yunusova Guzal Sultanovna //THE INFLUENCE OF THE MOTHER'S PERSONALITY IN RAISING THE SPIRITUAL CONSCIOUSNESS OF ADOLESCENTS// American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. Jun 9, 2022. 5, 111-115.
23. Yunusova Guzal Sultanovna //PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF CRIME PREVENTION AMONG TEENAGERS (FAMILY ASPECT)// American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, Oct 22, 2022. 9, 266-273 pages.
24. Гўзал Султоновна Юнусова, Исроилов Абборжон Ахатжон ўғли //ЎЗБЕКИСТОНЛИК ОЛИМЛАРНИНГ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАРИДА ОИЛАВИЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАР МУАММОСИНИНГ ЎРГАНИЛИШИ// Таълим ва инновацион тадқиқотлар. 2022 йил № 5. 284-287
25. Г.С.Юнусова //ВЛИЯНИЕ ВНУТРИСЕМЕЙНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ НА ГОТОВНОСТЬ К СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЖИЗНИ ДЕТЕЙ// The Way of Science. 2018. № 2 (48). 77-79 pages.
26. Г.С.Юнусова //РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ МОТИВАЦИИ ПО ОТНОШЕНИЮ К ПОДДЕРЖКЕ И ОДОБРЕНИЮ У ДЕТЕЙ ПОДРОСТКОВОГО И ЮНОШЕСКОГО ВОЗРАСТА, ВОСПИТЫВАЮЩИХСЯ В ПОЛНЫХ И НЕПОЛНЫХ СЕМЬЯХ// Социальные науки и общественное здоровье: теоретические подходы, эмпирические исследования, практические решения: материалы III международной научно-практической конференции 20-21 апреля 2013 года. Прага. 83-87 стр.
27. Sulonovna, Y. G. (2022). O'SMIRLARDA AGRESSIV XULQ ATVORNI NAMOYON BO'LISHIDA OILANING ROLI: Yunusova Guzal Sulonovna, Farg'ona davlat universiteti. Psixologiya kafedراس dotsenti, Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent Turdimatova Elnozа Erkinjon qizi, Fargona davlat universiteti. Psixologiya Ixtisosligi bo'yicha 2-bosqich magistratura talabasi. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (11), 378-381.
28. Yunusova, G. (2023). THE INFLUENCE OF PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIP ON THE FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S BEHAVIOR. В MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 2, Выпуск 11, сс. 162–170).
29. Мирзажонова Э.Т. (2023). ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И УСЛУГ ДЛЯ СЕМЕЙ С ДЕТЬМИ, ИМЕЮЩИХ ОСОБЕННОСТИ

В РАЗВИТИИ, НА БАЗЕ МАХАЛЛИ. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE, 2(20), 108-116.

30. Мирзажонова, Э.. (2023). ЖЕНЩИНЫ В РОЛИ КОНСУЛЬТАНТОВ-МАСЛАХАТЧИ - НОВЫЙ ТИП ЛИДЕРА КАК УЧИТЕЛЯ, ПОМОЩНИКА, ТРЕНЕРА. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 3(8), 38-44.

31. Eleonora Topvoldievna Mirzajonova, Odinaxon Rahmanovna Parpiyeva //Modern Special Preschool Education: Problems and Solutions// Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. Vol. 9. 06-2022. 100-106 pages.

32. 5. Мамажонова, S. (2023). O'SMIRLARDA ADDIKTIV XULQ SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 3(5), 173-178.

